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Large cell, short-term stability testing of Au-Mo-modified Ni/GDC for solid oxide co-electrolysis

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Abstract

Production of H₂ by electrochemical conversion of H₂O, through electrolysis can be achieved without expensive catalysts using Solid Oxide Electrolysis cells (SOECs). SOEC shows great dynamics to become commercially competitive against other electrolysis technologies (AEL, PEMEL), which are better established but more expensive and less efficient. On the other hand, SOECs are less mature and have issues regarding performance and durability that are currently important issues that need to be addressed. Indicatively, the latest State-of-the-Art (SoA) cells with NiO/YSZ and LSM as cathode and anode electrodes, respectively, show that the performance decreases for the H₂O electrolysis reaction, whereas for the H₂O/ CO₂ co-electrolysis process, the situation is even worse and the technology level is much behind than the commercialization thresholds.

In this respect, SElySOs project focuses on understanding the degradation and lifetime fundamentals on both SOFC electrodes. New electrode materials are developed, and the degradation mechanisms are investigated during the project. Overall, the target is to improve the stability, minimize the degradation and achieve better performance during H₂O electrolysis and CO₂ electrolysis. This paper presents short-term stability testing of large ESCs comprising Au-Mo-modified NiO/GDC compared with unmodified Ni-GDC as fuel electrode and LSCF as air electrode, under steam electrolysis operating conditions. The cells are tested in short stack configuration with metallic interconnects and sealing. The two stacks are operated with 0.5 A/ cm² at 835°C. The results show a positive effect of the Au-Mo modified cell stack on the degradation rates during the stability tests. The observed degradation rate for the 3Au-3Mo-modified fuel electrode stack was 300 mV/kh as compared to 700 mV/kh with the non-modified Ni/GDC stack.

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Introduction

Green hydrogen is a strong candidate for a sustainable fuel. While many energy sources can be used to produce hydrogen, water electrolysis is one of the possible ways to transform renewable and other non-fossil sources of energy into hydrogen. High temperature electrolysis of steam (HTE) consumes lesser electrical energy than electrolysis at low temperature due to its thermodynamic and electrochemical kinetic conditions. Reversely operated Solid Oxide Fuel Cell (SOFC) performs as a Solid Oxide Electrolysis Cell (SOEC) by which HTE is achievable. Extensive SOFC research has demonstrated that low electrode over voltages can be achieved even for higher current densities. [1-3].

Degradation is identified as one of the important issues of SOEC. Literature studies report that lowest long-term degradation of SOEC under practical operation as 1.7%/1000h during 3600h at 1 A/cm² [4]. This accounts for twice the degradation of similar cells under fuel cell operation. In order to reduce the degradation, polarization and degradation mechanisms must be clearly identified. This will help to optimize the cell architecture by modifying or replacing one or both the electrodes with alternative materials.

The prime objective of SElySOs is to develop more efficient electrodes and understand the processes that causes degradation on both SOEC electrodes, by combining experiments with theoretical modelling over an extended range of operating conditions. Moreover, the technical goal of the project is to identify the key design parameters and acquire the necessary knowledge to guide the development of new SOECs that are less prone to degradation with improved performance and stability.

The paper is aiming at presenting the comparative electrochemical performance of H₂O electrolysis process in SOEC stack using the Ni/GDC electrodes modified by small amount of gold and molybdenum [5].

1. Experiments

1.1 Cell preparation

75mm x 75mm, 90 μ m 3YSZ electrolytes from Kerafol were first screen printed with a Ce_{0.8}Gd_{0.2}O_{2- δ} (GDC) layer (65mm x 65mm, thickness ~ 3-4 μ m) on the oxygen electrode side and sintered at 1350 $^{\circ}$ C for 1h under air. Then, the fuel electrode was deposited by means of the screen printing method, see reference for details [5]. After the screen printing of the fuel electrode, the cells were calcined at 1150 $^{\circ}$ C/2 h. The preparation of the ternary 3wt.% Au – 3wt.% Mo-NiO/GDC powder was made with the Deposition – Co Precipitation (D.CP.) method, as reported in a previous study [5]. After that, a layer of La_{0.58}Sr_{0.4}Co_{0.2}Fe_{0.8}O_{3- δ} (LSCF) as oxygen electrode (63mm x 63mm, thickness ~ 30 μ m) was screen printed on the GDC//3YSZ and sintered at 1080 $^{\circ}$ C for 3 h under air. Finally, additional layers for current collection and electrical contact, Nickel on the fuel side and LSM on the oxygen side were also added by screen printed. The active area of the cells was 42.25 cm².

1.2 Experimental Set-up

The stack design used in the project was developed with special emphasis on electrolysis operation. Interconnects were formed by stamping 0.3mm AISI 441 Co-Ce pre-coated ferritic stainless steel purchased from Sandvik, Norway. The corrugated channels in the interconnect were formed with parallel flow directions (Co-flow). Nickel mesh of thickness 0.25 mm was used in the fuel side to improve the current collection and adjust the thickness.

Figure 1: Cross sectional details of SElySOs short stack test setup with single cell.

The cross-section details of the SElySOs stack design is shown in Figure 1. It has tubes for inlet and outlet of fuel as well as inlet for air sweep. The sequence of a single cell short stack building is shown in the Figure 2. Glass tape (Keraglas from Kerafol) was used to prevent gas leakage in the stack and towards the manifold.

The voltage measurements were performed using platinum wires connected to the interconnects, thus, the resistance measured in the current-voltage (I-V) curves consists of repeatable unit which in SOFC mode includes the following elements: electrolyte resistance, fuel electrode resistance, dilution of fuel with produced H₂O, gas diffusion resistance, air electrode resistance and horizontal current collection through the interconnect. The different elements in the resistance cannot be separated in DC experiments, thus several experiments were required to optimize the performance.

The stacks were heated as per the sealing glass firing schedule. After completing the firing schedule, the stack with the modified electrodes was reduced at 845°C and the stack with the non-modified electrodes was reduced at 835°C. After reduction, the stack temperature was reduced to 835°C. The reason is the glass sealing tape that is designed to operate below 840°C.

Figure 2: Sequence of a single cell stack assembly.

2. Results

2.1 Stack with Au-Mo-Ni/GDC fuel electrode

The stack with modified electrodes was operated at 830°C for 430 hours.

The initial I-V curve was recorded during fuel cell mode with fuel flow consisting of 90:10% of H₂ and N₂. Later the stack was operated with 50:50% of H₂ and H₂O. The I-V curves are recorded during fuel cell mode and electrolysis mode. The ASR values are shown in the Figure 6.

The long-term stack degradation is shown in Figure 4. The initial stack degradation measured for 250 hours was 300 mV/kh at a fuel utilisation of 37%. Later the stack was operated at higher fuel utilisation of 56% and experimented to operate without CO₂ supply first and later without the N₂ dilution of the fuel.

Figure 4: The stack degradation at various fuel utilization under constant current density.

Mass spectroscopy (MS) was used for analysis the exhaust from the stack. During steady state electrolysis operation, a hydrogen concentration of the dried gas of of 99% was reached, see Figure 5.

Figure 5: Variation of product composition obtained from Mass spectroscopy

2.1 Stack with non-modified Ni/GDC electrode

The 2 cells short stack with non-modified cells (NiO/GDC) is still under operation. The stack has been operated for 200 hours till now, mainly under water electrolysis. The I-V curve in Figure 6 shows the comparison between the modified stack and non-modified stack. We can see that the unmodified stack has a slightly higher resistance when compared to modified stack both during fuel cell mode and also during H₂O electrolysis mode.

Figure 7 shows the operational history of the unmodified stack. Operated initially for about 20 hrs. in fuel cell mode at a current density of 0,3 A/cm² and after that the stack is operated in H₂O electrolysis mode. The observed stack degradation was 700mV/kh.

Discussion

Figure 8 shows the degradation comparative data between the stack built using cells with Au-Mo-Ni/GDC electrode and non-modified NiO/GDC electrode. We can observe that the initial degradation for the modified stack, refer Figure 4, is 300 mV/kh whereas at the similar stage for the unmodified stack the degradation is higher i.e., 700 mV/kh. This degradation can origin for numerous of different processes, however, this is a clear indication that the degradation of the Ni/GDC electrode can be reduced through Au-Mo-modification [5].

Figure 6: The variation of I-V curve with and without modified fuel electrode stack.

Figure 7: Degradation curve of non-modified electrode stack.

Figure 8: The degradation curves of modified and non-modified Ni/GDC electrode stacks.

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